

Behavior of Educational Organizations in Education for Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT: This article deals with a literature review of internalizing Education of Sustainable Development (ESD) in Indonesia. The important point about ESD relates to the issue of how educational institutions, includes Indonesia should respond to the challenges and opportunities posed by the idea of sustainability. ESD aims at developing competencies that empower Individuals to reflect on their own actions, taking into account their current and future social, economic and environmental impacts, from a local and a global perspective. ESD has to be understood as an integral part of quality education, inherent in the concept of lifelong learning: All educational institutions – from preschool to tertiary education and in non-formal and informal education – can and should consider it their responsibility to deal intensively with matters of sustainable development and to foster the development of sustainability competencies. ESD is holistic and transformational education that addresses learning content and outcomes, pedagogy and the learning environment. Thus, ESD does not only integrate contents such as climate change, poverty and sustainable consumption into the curriculum; it also creates interactive, learner centred teaching and learning settings.

KEYWORDS: Behavior of Educational, Education for Sustainable Development

PRELIMINARY

Indonesia is one of the countries that are members of UNESCO. The United Nations Education, Scientific, Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations (UN) which has the main goal of increasing cooperation between countries in the fields of education, science and culture based on justice, the rule of law, human rights and essential freedoms (Article 1, UNESCO Constitution). UN Decade of Education is one of the institutions under the auspices of UNESCO which focuses on ESD (Education Sustainable Development). In the implementation of the UN Decade with Impact - 10 years of Education for Sustainable Development in Germany there is a statement regarding the main goal of the UN Decade is to apply ESD to schools, which is a standard for education plans, curriculum and frameworks. Education is the main pillar in shaping the mindset of the younger generation through ESD with the development of the concept of sustainability in three main aspects, namely, environmental, economic and social aspects, the goal is to fulfill human needs in the present without disturbing the fulfillment of human needs in the future. (Buckler & Creech, 2014). UN has shown special concern in implementing sustainable development at the education level in the form of developing educational ideas for sustainable development. Furthermore, the UN also encourages participating countries to participate in finding various ways to introduce education for sustainable development in schools.

(Giddings et al., 2002) Sustainable development is often considered as three main integrated pillars: environmental, economic and social. The three main aspects are mutually integrated in their implementation. With this, education based on sustainable development focuses on development issues that do not address environmental issues but also have coherence with social and economic issues. (Rauch, 2002) describes each dimension that is considered sustainable. Rauch The basis of sustainable development in the field of environment as the preservation of natural resources, which ensures the main function of the ecosystem. Then on sustainable social development as solidarity and cooperation between communities, and sustainable economic development, namely ensuring the quality of life through self and community development.

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a multidisciplinary concept that views the concept of sustainable development based on social, economic and environmental perspectives. This concept has been clearly implied in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System as well as in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia concerning the paradigm of national education regarding sustainable development. This paradigm states that through education it will produce humans who have noble character, and provide benefits for the universe. This concept aims to produce human beings

who are able to fulfill all their life needs by always paying attention to the needs of the current generation and future generations. This paradigm stimulates implementation for the sustainability of the entire universe (Culture, 2015)

Indonesia as a developing country has also shown a response to this condition. The President of Indonesia, Joko Widodo and the Committee have followed up with the Tempo, 2015 SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) program. The implementation of sustainable education in Indonesia needs to be strengthened to achieve the expected sustainable development goals. An alternative that can be done is to strengthen the concept of sustainable development at the education level.

In the implementation of ESD, several main problems were found. Several researchers have investigated how teachers understand the interconnections between the three dimensions of sustainable development. Academics in The Fields of Education for Sustainable Development: Their conceptions of sustainable development, is an international journal that focuses on the implementation of ESD. The main focus of the research is on the extent to which teachers understand the conception and implementation of ESD, the results of this study indicate that most teachers both at the primary and secondary levels have not been able to integrate the main conceptions of environmental, social and economic aspects. So that in its implementation, it is still separately by focusing on the environment then social and economic. Some researchers have also found that high school teachers in Sweden have difficulty integrating the three dimensions of the concept of sustainable development (Borg et al., 2014). Primary school teachers on duty in New Zealand, have a shallow and simple understanding of the concept of sustainable development (Birdsall, 2014). In the end, high school teachers in Sweden do not promote a holistic understanding of sustainable development when teaching, because they consider the lack of practices to inspire students and the lack of skills and abilities related to sustainable development practices (Borg et al., 2014)

(Sinakou et al., 2018) states that most teachers identify from the three aspects of ESD, that the closest to the idea of sustainable development is the concept of the environment. This is certainly contrary to the main concept of ESD, namely sustainability between environmental, social and economic aspects. This opinion is in line with (Listiwati, 2013) which is regarding the level of urgency of instilling ESD values in educational units by starting through an environmental approach and then exploring complex and holistically in the social and economic fields, because ESD is an integrated concept, not only consisting of one aspect. Simanjuntak (2017) states that education for sustainable development is not enough if the goal is only to build cognitive, what is needed by human development in sustainable development is the development of human character that focuses on the perspective of biocentrism, which is a paradigm that every life of living things has a valuable value in itself. Themselves in every moral action for the preservation of nature. Based on the argument of the ESD practice problem, the researchers tried to use it as a benchmark in the investigation of the extent to which holistic implementation is integrated in ESD practice and to measure the extent to which teachers and students understand at the elementary level, especially in elementary schools in the city of Bandar Lampung.

The focus of this research is to find an overview of the implementation of ESD practices in elementary schools. The process of integrating ESD practices which is then used by researchers as one aspect of observing ESD practices. Some of the main aspects that researchers are trying to explore more deeply are the extent to which teachers' understanding and perception in the implementation and presentation of ESD, as well as student responses in this regard.

METHOD

The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach with a comparative descriptive method. Comparative descriptive research method is research by discussing social symptoms or phenomena related to two or more variables, comparing or looking for differences in these variables and then describing them in depth. Field data obtained through this method can be interpreted and described in its entirety and in stages. During the process of preparing a research, it is necessary to form a design containing the steps or research procedures to make it easier for researchers to carry out the research phase. After the researcher obtained an overview of the research location, the researcher then compiled interview guidelines and documentation guidelines, research procedures, research procedures taken by researchers so that research could run well, including submitting a research permit. The primary data in this study were interviews with principals and teachers, then supplemented with secondary data, namely interviews with students and documentation of activities related to ESD in the form of photos and archives. The data collection technique used is snowball sampling.

Data analysis techniques in this study use Triangulation, Data Reduction (data reduction), Data Presentation (data display) and Verification (conclusion drawing). Then to show the validity of the data, the techniques used are, Credibility, Transferability, Dependability and Confirmability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ESD promotes competencies such as critical thinking, imagining future scenarios and making decisions in a collaborative way. Education for sustainable development is also an important pedagogical tool because it is based on the basic principle of making individuals see and recognize the interdependence between humans and each ecological unit. The 1987 Brundtland Report also makes a very important point in this context which states that sustainable development requires meeting the basic needs of all and expanding all opportunities to fulfill their aspirations for a better life. The role of ESD is based on three pillars; Social, environmental and economic are very important in changing the general perception and attitude of people towards self, social and environment.

Education for sustainable development is a tool to address interrelated objectives such as: 1. Social: to increase understanding of social institutions and their role in change and development, to promote social justice, gender equality, human rights, democratic and participatory systems, and health care (including HIV/AIDS). 2. Environment: to raise awareness of the resources and fragility of the physical environment, the impact of human activities on the environment, climate change, environmental protection (including water education), and biodiversity. 3. Economy: to create sensitivity to the potential and limits of economic growth, its impact on society and the environment, responsible and sustainable consumption, and rural development.

Education for sustainable development is actually an idea that comes from environmental education. The goal of ESD is to enable people to make decisions and take action to improve the quality of our lives without compromising the planet. It also aims to integrate the values inherent in sustainable development into all aspects and levels of learning. Famous figures such as Mahatma Gandhi, in this case have played a role in contributing his thoughts to promote environmental-based education. Gandhi focused on developing and consuming local products which were readily available in India at that time. In addition, in the International Union for Conservation of Nature (Ajaps and McLellan, 2015), environmental education is a process of introducing values and concepts with the aim of building the skills and attitudes needed to understand and appreciate the relationships between culture and the biophysical environment. Environmental education also conducts behavioral practices in making decisions regarding issues related to environmental quality.

The concept of sustainable development seeks to combine environmental care with social and economic development. This concept became familiar to the public in the 1980s with the Our Common Future report, also known as the 1987 Brundtland report. Until then, environmental protection had been the focus, arising from sharp environmental problems such as pollution. With the concept of SD (Sustainable Development), it is emphasized that environmental problems must be addressed related to social and economic problems. SD (Sustainable Development) is, in today's society, the overarching goal of balancing the well-being and improvement of people's lives globally in space and time, while at the same time conserving natural resources and ecosystems. continue to move further on the horizon. Nevertheless, this is a goal that the international community has successfully agreed to and pursued. Common policy documents have been decided and implemented internationally and nationally in most countries

Actions for a sustainable future can be considered at government, business, organizational and citizen levels. In the current paper we investigate the individual level. From an educational perspective all outcomes and assessments are carried out at the individual level, and the steering document for the Swedish school system on ESD should also be evaluated at the individual level. Therefore if investigating the effect of ESD in Swedish schools it should reflect the overall goals of the organization and we therefore zoom in at the individual level.

It is widely accepted that most examples of deteriorating environmental conditions are caused by human behavior. The drivers of sustainability problems are rarely the result of malicious intent, but rather a consequence of the lifestyles of billions of people. (Schultz, 2011) argues that SD is "a goal that can only be achieved by changing behavior". Those behavioral actions can work on different societal levels from individual personal lifestyle, to political decision making, or business closures etc and thus have different powers in making a difference for sustainable development. Moreover, behaviors that support SD (Sustainable Development) are held back by structural and cultural barriers as pointed out by (Isenhour, 2010). Nevertheless, the behavior of individual citizens is a construct that has been widely studied in the social sciences, and while scholars may disagree the most applicable empirical model to explain the cause, there is a great consensus that it correlates with individual psychological

characteristics, such as attitudes and knowledge. Particularly relevant is the study of these constructs in young people, early in their lives as active citizens and future leaders (Ginwright & James, 2002), from habit consolidation, behavioral patterns (Moreno et al., 2008), and identity formation and interpersonal relationships (Blakemore, 2008). In the current study, we focused on student sustainability awareness or SC (Olsson et al., 2013). The SC concept is a composite idea, unifying content in environmental, social, and economics, as well as psychological constructs related to knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to these problems. The SC concept was developed in relation to the UNESCO subthemes outlined. To achieve a transition to a sustainable future, essential ingredients for change at the individual citizen level include a better understanding of, more positive attitudes towards, and behavior in line with the SD principles. The question that must then be answered is how to achieve this ambitious goal? How can we change the course of our future? One of the clearest answers to this question in the last decade has been: education.

Educational efforts aim to empower students' action competencies to address these critical ingredients for change. Action competence is considered to be closely related to knowledge of the possibility of action, belief in one's own influence, and willingness to act (Breiting & Mogensen, 1999). SC, with its distinct psychological components built on this definition by (Breiting & Mogensen, 1999). The SC concept is considered to reflect the student's sustainability action competence.

Education for Sustainable Development

By educating citizens, especially the younger generation in the formal school system, the hope is effectively of SD issues (Sustainable Development) (Bonnett, 1999). This hope led to the launch of the Un Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD), overseen by UNESCO. During this Decade, ESD was launched as an approach to teaching and learning that promotes SD. ESD has evolved from an idea into a global movement (Hopkins, 2012), and understanding of what it is or should be has evolved during DESD. UNESCO's definition reads: "Education for Sustainable Development means including key sustainable development issues into teaching and learning; for example, climate change, disaster risk reduction, biodiversity, poverty reduction, and sustainable consumption. This also requires participatory teaching and learning methods. Which motivates and empowers learners to change their behavior and take action for sustainable development. Education for Sustainable Development consequently promotes competencies such as critical thinking, imagining future scenarios and making decisions collaboratively"

In this definition we can trace two important features of ESD: the first deal with content, the second with pedagogy. Both are well recognized in the literature: "ESD continues to grow in both content and pedagogy and its visibility and respectability have grown in parallel" (Hopkins, 2012). As seen in the UNESCO definition, ESD content spans a wide range of disciplines: climate change, poverty reduction, consumption etc., and interdisciplinary is very important to understand the complexity of SD problems (Sustainable Development (Mathew, RV, & Panchanatham, N. 2016. An exploratory study on the development of women entrepreneurs: Indian cases. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship* et al., 2018). In the ESD literature this idea is labeled holism or a holistic approach because it includes several perspectives on content. (Gough, 2002) The holistic perspective of SD (Sustainable Development) recognizes that social and cultural factors often become the cause of environmental problems, and there are often conflicts of interest between the economic, social, and environmental goals of individuals and communities (Borg et al., 2014). Such conflicts span not only scientific disciplines, they also bind local and global perspectives as well as past generations, present, and future. In the outline of ESD as a teaching tradition (Rudsberg & hman, 2010) identify three important aspects of holism: linking the environmental, social, and economic dimensions of SD (Sustainable Development) problems, integrating past, present and future implications. Their future, and focus on their local, regional, and global nature.

The second important feature of ESD relates to the teaching and learning process. ESD focuses on developing skills and competencies for action for sustainability (Breiting & Mogensen, 1999). This pedagogy has been labeled pluralism (Lijmbach et al., 2002), and is characterized by an attempt to recognize and involve different perspectives, views, and values when dealing with SD (Sustainable Development) issues. The underlying idea is that the complexity of the problem and the conflict of interest make it impossible to teach a predetermined solution. Instead of teaching "correct" answers and responses to SD, ESD focuses on reflecting on problems (Lijmbach et al., 2002). This progressive and transformative pedagogical approach develops students' critical evaluation of alternative perspectives and calls for learner centred teaching strategies (e.g., critical thinking, participatory decision-making, values-based learning, and multi-method approaches; (Rudsberg & hman, 2010), and social learning. Basically, ESD aims to facilitate learning in such a way that learners understand the world based on their own observations, and develop competencies to take action for sustainability. Holism and pluralism are often seen as intricately intertwined. Learning is thought to take place through

tapping pluralistic social perspectives, the economy, and the environment (Englund, 2006). These two important features of ESD have been recognized as challenges for teachers and schools seeking to implement ESD.

In the literature there is an emphasis on encouraging holism and pluralism for deliberation on ESD. It is argued that unless ESD and discourse on SD (Sustainable Development) remain open to educators' opinions and debates, it risks becoming indoctrinated (Rudsberg & hman, 2010) Therefore holism and pluralism in education are suggested as important to promote SD (Sustainable Development), and therefore in the main focus of our current study, where we focus on investigating the implementation of ESD in the context of formal education in Sweden.

Integration of ESD into Curriculum

ESD should be integrated into all formal education curricula, including early childhood education, primary and secondary education, technical and vocational education and training, as well as higher education. ESD is at the core of teaching and learning and should not be considered as an addition to the existing curriculum. In this case, ESD requires not only the integration of sustainability topics into the curriculum, but also learning outcomes related to sustainability. ESD should not be seen as an adjective education or an isolated standalone subject.

For example in school education, it should be an integral part of the teaching and learning of core subjects (e.g. mathematics, science, social sciences and languages).

Second, it is important that learning objectives, teaching and learning methods and assessment measures are closely aligned so that they reinforce each other. Third, progressive learning objectives must be set, namely learning that builds competence from level to level (scaffolding).

Integration of ESD to Teachers/Educators Materials that can provide the educational response needed to achieve the SDGs. Their knowledge and competencies are very important to restructure educational processes and educational institutions towards sustainability. Teachers are required to face this challenge by reorienting themselves towards ESD. However, efforts to prepare teachers to implement ESD are still not sufficiently advanced. There is still much work to be done to direct teachers towards education for sustainable development, both in terms of content, teaching and learning methods.

In order for teachers to be ready to facilitate ESD, teachers must develop ongoing key competencies (including knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, motivation, and commitment). Besides general sustainability competencies, they also need ESD competencies, which can be described as the capacity of teachers to help people develop sustainability competencies through innovative teaching and learning practices. To facilitate the development of ESD competencies in teacher education, changes in the content and structure of pre-service and in-service teacher education are needed. ESD should provide a fundamental orientation to teacher education programs. Subject disciplines, didactic subjects, educational sciences and practice-oriented studies should incorporate the methodological principles and subject knowledge of ESD. Learning on the basis of real social challenges in local contexts requires working with external partners. Modules should allow access to external partners (such as communities, non-formal education institutions and ESD networks) and include possibilities for project-oriented collaboration.

ESD Concepts in Learning

ESD doesn't just teach continuous development or add new content to courses and training. Schools and universities must act as places of learning or places of experience for sustainable development and therefore must orient all processes towards the principle of sustainability. For ESD to be more effective, educational institutions as a whole must be transformed. This holistic institutional approach aims to mainstream sustainability into all aspects of educational institutions. This involves rethinking curriculum, campus operations, organizational culture, student participation, leadership and management, public relations and research (UNESCO, in Rieckmann, 2017). In this way, the institution itself serves as a role model for learners. Sustainable learning environments, such as eco-schools or green campuses, enable educators and students to integrate sustainability principles into their daily practice and facilitate comprehensive capacity building, competency development and value education.

CONCLUSION

Sustainable development is not only a way to overcome environmental crises, but also social and economic crises experienced in various parts of the world. One form of education that can have a major impact on development is Education for Sustainable

Development (ESD). Education for Sustainable Development enables every human being to acquire the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to shape a sustainable future.

The implementation of ESD in each school has various variations according to the school's perception. The condition of the school background is correlated with efforts to implement ESD practices. The supporting factor for the implementation of ESD in elementary schools is if the school has a good concept and implementation related to aspects of school policy, school strategy, conception of implementing components and commitment to implementing activities. The inhibiting factor for the implementation of ESD in elementary schools is if the school does not have good policies and strategies related to ESD development and a low level of awareness regarding the conception and commitment to implementing ESD-based activities

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Birdsall, S. (2014). Measuring student teachers' understandings and self-awareness of sustainability. *Environmental Education Research*, 20(6), 814–835.
2. Blakemore, S.-J. (2008). The social brain in adolescence. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 9(4), 267–277.
3. Bonnett, M. (1999). Education for sustainable development: a coherent philosophy for environmental education? *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 29(3), 313–324.
4. Borg, C., Gericke, N., Höglund, H.-O., & Bergman, E. (2014). Subject-and experience-bound differences in teachers' conceptual understanding of sustainable development. *Environmental Education Research*, 20(4), 526–551.
5. Breiting, S., & Mogensen, F. (1999). Action competence and environmental education. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 29(3), 349–353.
6. Buckler, C., & Creech, H. (2014). *Shaping the future we want: UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development; final report*. Unesco.
7. Englund, T. (2006). Deliberative communication: A pragmatist proposal. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 38(5), 503–520.
8. Giddings, B., Hopwood, B., & O'brien, G. (2002). Environment, economy and society: fitting them together into sustainable development. *Sustainable Development*, 10(4), 187–196.
9. Ginwright, S., & James, T. (2002). From assets to agents of change: Social justice, organizing, and youth development. *New Directions for Youth Development*, 2002(96), 27–46.
10. Gough, S. (2002). Right answers or wrong problems? Towards a theory of change for environmental learning. *The Trumpeter*, 18(1).
11. Hopkins, C. (2012). *Twenty years of education for sustainable development*. SAGE Publications Sage India: New Delhi, India.
12. Isenhour, C. (2010). On conflicted Swedish consumers, the effort to stop shopping and neoliberal environmental governance. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 9(6), 454–469.
13. Kebudayaan, K. P. D. (2015). *Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 84 Tahun 2014*. Jakarta: KEMENDIKBUD.
14. Lijmbach, S., Van Arcken, M. M., Van Koppen, C. S. A., & Wals, A. E. J. (2002). "Your View of Nature is Not Mine!": learning about pluralism in the classroom. *Environmental Education Research*, 8(2), 121–135.
15. Listiawati, N. (2013). Pelaksanaan Pendidikan untuk Pembangunan Berkelanjutan Oleh Beberapa Lembaga. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan*, 19(3), 430–450.
16. Mathew, R. V., & Panchanatham, N. 2016. An exploratory study on the development of women entrepreneurs: Moreno, L. A., De Henauw, S., Gonzalez-Gross, M., Kersting, M., Molnar, D.,
17. Gottrand, F., Barrios, L., Sjöström, M., Manios, Y., & Gilbert, C. C. (2008). Design and implementation of the healthy lifestyle in Europe by nutrition in adolescence cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Obesity*, 32(5), S4–S11.
18. Olsson, D., Gericke, N., & ChangRundgren, S.-N. (2013). Young people and their integrated understanding of sustainable development. *10 th ESERA Conference in Nicosia, Cyprus 2-7 September*.
19. Rauch, F. (2002). The potential of education for sustainable development for reform in schools. *Environmental Education Research*, 8(1), 43–51. Rudsberg, K., & Öhman, J. (2010).

20. Pluralism in practice—experiences from Swedish evaluation, school development and research. *Environmental Education Research*, 16(1), 95–111.
21. Schultz, P. W. (2011). Conservation means behavior. *Conservation Biology*, 25(6), 1080–1083.
22. Sinakou, E., Boeve-de Pauw, J., Goossens, M., & Van Petegem, P. (2018). Academics in the field of Education for Sustainable Development: Their conceptions of sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 184, 321–332.